

Instructions: each row specifies what to eat at each meal time. You may choose a single box in each row and all within the same meal time are equivalent and exchangeable.

TIME	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
8:00 a.m.	Banana - 1 piece (2 Fruit SFS)	Strawberry Papaya smoothie - 1 cup strawberries (1 Fruit SFS) - 1 cup papaya (1 Fruit SFS)	Pear - 1 piece (2 Fruit SFS)	Grapes - 36 pieces (2 Fruit SFS)	Apple - 1 piece (1 Fruit SFS) Kiwi - 1 piece (1 Fruit SFS)	Grapefruit - 1 piece (1 Fruit SFS) Watermelon - 1 cup watermelon (1 Fruit SFS)	Berries - 1 cup berry mix (1 Fruit SFS) Melon - 1 cup melon (1 Fruit SFS)
	Pancakes - 2 small pieces of 40g each (2 Cereal B SFS) - 1 tsp. butter (1 Fat A SFS) - 3 tsp. maple syrup (1.5 Sugar A SFS)	Toasted bread with jam and butter - 2 whole wheat bread slices - 3 tsp. butter (2 Cereal B SFS + 1 Fat A SFS) - 3 tsp. jam (1.5 Sugar SFS)	Waffle - 2 small pieces of 40g each (2 Cereal B SFS) - 1 tsp. butter (1 Fat A SFS) - 3 tsp. maple syrup (1.5 Sugar SFS)	Toasted bread with jam and cream cheese - 2 whole wheat bread slices - 3 tbsp. cream cheese (2 Cereal B SFS + 1 Fat A SFS) - 4 tsp. jam (1.5 Sugar SFS)	Croissant - 1 piece of 60g (2 Cereal B SFS + 1 Fat A SFS) - 4 tsp. jam (1.5 Sugar SFS)	Apple Strudel - 1 piece of 70g (2 Cereal B SFS + 1 Fat A SFS) - 4 tsp. jam (1.5 Sugar SFS)	Bagel with jam and cream cheese - 1 whole wheat bagel of 50g - 3 tbsp. cream cheese (2 Cereal B SFS + 1 Fat A SFS) - 4 tsp. jam (1.5 Sugar SFS)
11:00 a.m.	Grapes - 18 pieces (1 Fruit SFS)	Apple - 1 piece (1 Fruit SFS)	Melon - 1 cup melon (1 Fruit SFS)	Orange - 2 pieces (1 Fruit SFS)	Watermelon - 1 cup watermelon (1 Fruit SFS)	Tangerine - 2 pieces (1 Fruit SFS)	Strawberries - 1 cup (1 Fruit SFS)
	Almonds – 10 pieces (1 Fat B SFS) Crystallized Fruit – 3 pieces (1 Sugar SFS)	Peanut Butter – 1 tbsp. (1 Fat B SFS) Marshmallows – 2 big pieces (15g) (1 Sugar SFS)	Pistachio – 18 pieces (1 Fat B SFS) Lolly Pop – 1 piece (1 Sugar SFS)	Honey Roasted Peanuts – 15 pieces (1 Fat B SFS + 1 Sugar SFS)	Nuts – 3 pieces (1 Fat B SFS) Jelly – ½ cup (1 Sugar SFS)	Almond Butter – 1 tbsp. (1 Fat B SFS) Mini Marshmallows – 18 pieces (15g) (1 Sugar SFS)	Hazelnut Cream – 1 tbsp. (1 Fat B SFS + 1 Sugar SFS)
2:00 p.m.	Watermelon Water - 1 cup watermelon (1 Fruit SFS) - 2 tsp. sugar (1 Sugar SFS) - Free amount of water	Pineapple-Cucumber Water - 1 cup pineapple (1 Fruit SFS) - 2 tsp. sugar (1 Sugar SFS) - Free amount of water - ½ cucumber piece (1/2 Vegetable SFS) - ½ lemon piece	Strawberry Lemonade - 1 cup strawberries (1 Fruit SFS) - 2 tsp. sugar (1 Sugar SFS) - Free amount of water - 1 lemon piece	Kiwi Lemonade - 1 kiwi (1 Fruit SFS) - 2 tsp. sugar (1 Sugar SFS) - Free amount of water - 1 lemon piece	Tangerine Water - 2 tangerine pieces (1 Fruit SFS) - 2 tsp. sugar (1 Sugar SFS) - Free amount of water	Berry Lemonade - 1 cup berries (1 Fruit SFS) - 2 tsp. sugar (1 Sugar SFS) - Free amount of water - 1 lemon piece	Orange Water - 1 orange piece (1 Fruit SFS) - 2 tsp. sugar (1 Sugar SFS) - Free amount of water
	Avocado Green Salad - 1/3 avocado piece (1 Fat A SFS) - 1 cup vegetables: spinach, cucumber, bell pepper and alfalfa (1 Vegetable SFS) Chicken Fajitas - 50g chicken breast (2 AO A SFS) - 1 tsp. oil (1 Fat A SFS) - 1 cup vegetables: Bell pepper, onion and mushrooms (1 Vegetable SFS) Whole Beans - ½ cup (1 Leguminous SFS) Steamed Pasta - 1 cup (2 Cereal A SFS)	Asparagus with Butter - 1 tsp. butter (1 Fat A SFS) - 1 cup asparagus (1 Vegetable SFS) Pan Seared Salmon - 60g salmon (2 AO A SFS) - 1 tsp. oil (1 Fat A SFS) - 1 cup vegetables: spinach and mushrooms (1 Vegetable SFS) Lentils - ½ cup (1 Leguminous SFS) Steamed Pasta - 1 cup (2 Cereal A SFS)	Caesar's Salad with Chicken - 40g chicken breast (1 AO A SFS) - 3 cups lettuce (1 Vegetable SFS) - 2 tsp. parmesan cheese (1 AO A SFS + ½ Fat SFS) - 1 tsp. ranch dressing (2 Fat SFS) - 1 cup bread croutons (2 Cereal SFS) Garlic-cilantro black bean salad - Free amount garlic and cilantro - ½ cup beans (1 Leguminous SFS)	Chickpea Salad - 1 cup vegetables: carrot, mushrooms, tomato, (1 Vegetable SFS) - ½ cup chickpea (1 Leguminous SFS) - 1 tsp. olive oil (1 Fat A SFS) - 1/3 avocado piece (1 Fat A SFS) Lasagna - 1 cup of steamed pasta (2 Cereal SFS) - 30g cooked ground beef (1 AO A SFS) - 40g mozzarella (1 AO A SFS) - ½ cup tomato sauce (1 Vegetable SFS)	Spinach with whole beans - ½ cup beans (1 Leguminous SFS) - 2 tsp. oil (2 Fat A SFS) - 1 cup vegetables: spinach, onion and garlic (1 Vegetable SFS) Chicken noodle soup - 50g chicken breast (2 AO A SFS) - 1 cup vegetables: carrot, pumpkin, Garlic, onion and celery (1 Vegetable SFS) - 1 cup noodles (2 Cereal A SFS)	Lentils - ½ cup (1 Leguminous SFS) Chicken Stew - 50g chicken breast (2 AO A SFS) - 2 tsp. avocado oil (2 Fat A SFS) - 1 cup steamed vegetables (carrot, onion, pea, tomato) (2 Vegetable SFS) - 1 baked potato (2 Cereal A SFS)	Avocado Salad - 1/3 avocado piece (1 Fat A SFS) - 2 cups vegetables: spinach, cucumber, tomato, mushrooms, bell pepper and alfalfa (2 Vegetable SFS) Lemon pepper fish - 80g tilapia (2 AO A SFS) - Free amount lemon juice, garlic and pepper - 1 tsp. olive oil (1 Fat A SFS) Cooked brown rice - 2/3 cup (2 Cereal A SFS) Whole Beans - ½ cup (1 Leguminous SFS)
	Apple - 1 piece (1 Fruit SFS)	Melon - 1 cup melon (1 Fruit SFS)	Orange - 2 pieces (1 Fruit SFS)	Watermelon - 1 cup watermelon (1 Fruit SFS)	Tangerine - 2 pieces (1 Fruit SFS)	Strawberries - 1 cup (1 Fruit SFS)	Grapes - 18 pieces (1 Fruit SFS)
5:00 p.m.	Orange - 2 pieces (1 Fruit SFS)	Watermelon - 1 cup watermelon (1 Fruit SFS)	Tangerine - 2 pieces (1 Fruit SFS)	Strawberries - 1 cup (1 Fruit SFS)	Grapes - 18 pieces (1 Fruit SFS)	Apple - 1 piece (1 Fruit SFS)	Melon - 1 cup melon (1 Fruit SFS)
	Pistachios – 18 pieces (1 Fat B SFS)	Nuts – 3 pieces (1 Fat B SFS)	Peanuts – 15 pieces (1 Fat B SFS)	Almond Butter – 1 tbsp. (1 Fat B SFS)	Almonds – 10 pieces (1 Fat B SFS)	Peanut Butter – 1 tbsp. (1 Fat B SFS)	Sesame – 4 tsp. (1 Fat B SFS)
8:00 p.m.	Tomato – 1 piece (1 Vegetable SFS)	Cucumber – 1 cup (1 Vegetable SFS)	Lettuce – 3 cups (1 Vegetable SFS)	Spinach – 1 cup (1 Vegetable SFS)	Carrot – 1 cup (1 Vegetable SFS)	Bell pepper – 1 cup (1 Vegetable SFS)	Alfalfa – 1 cup (1 Vegetable SFS)
	Boiled egg - 2 egg whites (1 AO A SFS) Toasted bread with butter - 1 slice of whole bread (1 Cereal A SFS) - 1 tsp. butter (1 Fat A SFS)	Avocado Tuna - 30g tuna (1 AO A SFS) - 1/3 avocado (1 Fat A SFS) - 1 slice whole bread (1 Cereal A SFS)	Sandwich - 25g ham (1 AO A SFS) - 1 tsp. mayonnaise (1 Fat A SFS) - 1 slice whole bread (1 Cereal A SFS)	Cheese Avocado sandwich - 40g low fat cheese mozzarella (1 AO A SFS) - 1/3 avocado (1 Fat A SFS) - 1 slice whole bread (1 Cereal A SFS)	Sushi - 30g tuna (1 AO A SFS) - 1/3 avocado (1 Fat A SFS) - 1/3 cup rice (1 Cereal A SFS)	Flat Bread Pizza - 40g low fat cheese mozzarella (1 AO A SFS) - 1/3 bacon slice (1 Fat A SFS) - ½ flat bread – (1 Cereal A SFS)	Wrap Avocado - 40g low fat cheese mozzarella (1 AO A SFS) - 1/3 avocado (1 Fat A SFS) - ½ flat bread (1 Cereal A SFS)